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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to concepts, etiopathogenesis, types of clinical course, modern diagnosis and treatment of reflux-esophagitis, which is one of the main problems of modern medicine and surgery. These diseases occur in more than 35-40% of the world's population. The article presents modern surgical, endoscopic and therapeutic methods of treatment of diseases.

Key words: Hiatal hernia, GERD, reflux-esophagitis, endoscopy

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REFLYUKS-EZOFAGIT TUSHUNCHASI, ZAMONAVIY TASHXISLASH VA DAVOLASH**ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqola zamonaviy tibbiyot va jarrohlikning asosiy muammolaridan biri diafragma

qizilo'ngach teshigi churralari (DQTCh) asorati hisoblangan reflyuks-ezofagit haqida tushunchalar, etiopatogenezi, klinik kechish turlari, zamonaviy tashxislash va davolashga bag'ishlangan. Bu kasalliklar dunyo aholisining 35-40% dan ortig'ida uchraydi. Maqolada kasalliklarning zamonaviy jarrohlik, endoskopik va terapevtik davolash usullari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: DQTCh, GERK, reflyuks-ezofagit, endoskopiya.

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РЕФЛЮКС-ЭЗОФАГИТ: СОВРЕМЕННАЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА И ЛЕЧЕНИЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена понятиям, этиопатогенезу, типам клинического течения, современной диагностике и лечению рефлюкс-эзофагита, который является одной из основных проблем современной медицины и хирургии. Эти заболевания встречаются более чем у 35-40% населения земного шара. В статье представлены современные хирургические, эндоскопические и терапевтические методы лечения заболеваний.

Ключевые слова: ГПОД, ГЭРБ, рефлюкс-эзофагит, эндоскопия..

"Gastroezophageal reflyuks kasalligi" (GERK) atamasi 1966 yilda J. Rossetti tomonidan taklif qilingan. Bu atama oshqozon yoki o'n ikki barmoqli ichak tarkibining qizilo'ngachga doimiy reflyuksi (regurgitatsiyasi) natijasida qizilo'ngachning distal qismidagi yallig'lanish o'zgarishini va bir qator ko'plab alomatlarni tavsiflaydi. Bu asoratlarni jamlab, reflyuks-ezofagit klinik atamasini hosil qilish mumkin [1, 5, 14, 18, 22].

1997 yil Genval shahrida o'tkazilgan (Belgiya) butunjahon fanlararo kongressda, GERK mustaqil nozologik kasallik sifatida tan olingan. Hozirgi vaqtda GERK atamasi ko'pincha diafragma qizilo'ngach teshigi churrasi (DQTCh) bilan birga qo'llaniladi [4, 9, 17, 21].

Ko'pgina terapevtlarning fikriga ko'ra, GERKni konservativ davo bilan davolash mumkin. Ammo 6 oydan so'ng kasallikning qaytalanishi ko'rsatgichi 50% dan oshadi va bir yildan keyin u hatto 90% ga yetishi mumkin. Shuning uchun bu patologiyani jarrohlik yo'li bilan davolash GERKni davolashda asosiy usullardan biridir [8, 11, 20, 25].

Refluks ezofagitning etiologiyasi va patogenezi. Sontag S.J.ga binoan Refluks ezofagit (RE) rivojlanishda uchta asosiy mexanizmga bo'linadi:

1. Pastki qizilo'ngach sfinkterining (PQS) rivojlanishining tug'ma nuqsoni. Antirefluks to'siq, shu jumladan silliq mushak PQS, chiziqli mushak diafragma krarasi va qizilo'ngach membranasini, intrauterin malformatsiya yoki anormal homiladorlik tufayli normal shakllanmaydi.

2. O'tkir shikastlanish. O'tkir travma (yo'l-transport hodisasi paytida qorin yoki ko'krak qafasining shikastlanishi, zarba, og'ir narsalarni ko'tarish) tufayli antirefluks to'siq buziladi. Travma diafragma qizilo'ngach teshigi churrasirivojlanishiga olib keladi, bu esa antirefluks to'siqni GERKni oldini olishga qodir emas.

3. Surunkali shikastlanish. Bolalar va kattalardagi reflyuksga qarshi to'siq vaqt o'tishi bilan ichak harakati paytida surunkali zo'riqish va fiziologik bo'lmagan sharoitlarda kuchlanish (tolaning kamligi, harakatsiz turmush tarzi) tufayli asta-sekin zaiflashadi. Bu omillar, shuningdek, keyinchalik refluks ezofagit paydo bo'lishi bilan diafragma qizilo'ngach teshigi churrasirivojlanishiga olib keladi [2, 7, 12, 16].

RE bilan oshqozon yoki o'n ikki barmoqli ichak tarkibining qizilo'ngachga surunkali refluyksiyasi paydo bo'ladi. Qizilo'ngachning moslashtirilmagan shilliq qavatining regurgitatsiyalangan kislotali yoki ishqoriy sekretsiyalar bilan uzoq vaqt aloqasi tufayli qizilo'ngach devorida patologik morfologik o'zgarishlar yuzaga keladi. Shu bilan birga, oshqozon tarkibidagi refluyks sog'lom odamlarda ham kuzatiladi, ammo bu qisqa muddatli va himoya mexanizmlari xlorid kislotasini tezda neytrallashtiradi. Zamonaviy qarashlarga ko'ra, himoya va agressiv omillar o'rtasidagi nomutanosiblik RE rivojlanishiga olib keladi [6, 19]

Barrettning qizilo'ngachini (BQ) aniqlash chastotasi populyatsiyada o'rtacha 2,1 dan 4% gacha. Kasallikning etiologik omillari quyidagilardir: hayot sifatining yomonlashishi, tamaki chekish, spirtli ichimliklarni iste'mol qilish, qizilo'ngachning qatlamli yassi epiteliysiga zarar etkazadigan turli xil dorilar (xususan, siklofosfamid, 5-fluorourasil bilan kimyoterapiya paytida), gastroezofageal [3, 10, 24].

RE kabi BQ patogenezing asosiy bo'g'ini patologik refluyksning paydo bo'lishiga olib keladigan vosita buzilishlaridir. Pastki qizilo'ngach sfinkteri (PQS) mintaqadagi bosimning pasayishi va funktsiyalarning etishmasligi tufayli oldini olishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. (PQS) qizilo'ngachning motor funktsiyasining buzilishiga olib keladi, qizilo'ngach klirensining pasayishi, shuningdek, RE belgilari paydo bo'lish davomiyligi va chastotasining oshishi [2, 15, 23].

Klinik kechishi. RE ning klinik ko'rinishi morfologik o'zgarishlar darajasiga, asoratlar va birga keladigan kasalliklarning mavjudligiga bog'liq. 2005 yilda Monreal konsensusiga ko'ra RE tasnifi qayta ko'rib chiqildi va RE ning "asosiy" (qizilo'ngach) va "ekstraefozageal" (atipik) belgilarini farqlash tavsiya etildi [5, 12, 24, 25].

Asosiy (qizilo'ngachli) belgilariga RE quyidagilarni anglatadi :

- jig'ildon qaynashi (70-100%) .
- kekirish (75-96%),
- epigastriy va to'sh orqasida og'riq (20-56%),
- regurjitatsiya, disfagiya (17-22%).

Shuningdek, ovqatlanayotganda reflector stenokardiya belgilari (Uden-Ramheld sindromi) va qon ketish (ayniqsa, diafragma qizilo'ngach teshigi churrasi bilan) kuzatilishi mumkin.

Atipik (qizilo'ngach bo'lmagan) alomatlariga quyidagilar kiradi:

1. Ko'krakdagi nokardial og'riq ko'pincha qizilo'ngach kasalliklari bilan bog'liq. Ulardan 60% RE bilan kuzatiladi. Har yili 600 000 ga yaqin amerikaliklar koronar angiografiyadan o'tadilar. Ulardan 10-30% koronar tomirlarning patologiyasiga ega emas.

2. Otolaringeal simptomlar-ovozning xirillashi va odatiy yo'tal ham RE bilan bog'liq. Poelmans J. va boshq., o'rta otitda RE namoyon bo'lishining 4 ta holati haqida xabar bering. Koufman J. A. Turli xil otolaringologik kasalliklari bo'lgan 225 bemorning pH-metriyasida 62% REga xos bo'lgan patologik pH ko'rsatkichlarini qayd etdi. El-Serag N.V. va boshqalar RE laringeal va faringeal saraton rivojlanishi uchun xavf omili ekanligiga ishonishadi.

3. O'pka belgilari: takroriy bronxial astma. Ba'zi tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, surunkali yo'talning taxminan 40% RE tufayli yuzaga kelishi isbotlangan [9, 13, 18].

Klinik ko'rinishlariga ko'ra, BQ belgilari RE belgilariga o'xshaydi (yurakning yonishi, ko'krak qafasidagi og'riq va noqulaylik, regurgitatsiya, disfagiya). Biroq, ba'zi farqlar mavjud - metaplastik epiteliyning past sezgirligi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan va epiteliyani qayta qurishning "himoya funktsiyasi" deb hisoblangan noqulaylik va jig'ildon qaynashining yo'qolishi yoki kamayishi [4, 16, 23].

Refluks ezofagit diagnostikasining so'nggi zamonaviy usullari. Qizilo'ngachning rentgenologik tekshiruv RE asosiy tashxisining yetakchi usullaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda, garchi bu tadqiqot usulining sezgirligi o'rtacha 70-72% ni tashkil qilsa ham. Shuningdek, rentgen tekshiruv bilan churraning tabiati, hajmi, harakatchanligi yoki harakatsizligini aniqlash mumkin, shuningdek, churra qopidagi oshqozondan tashqari boshqa a'zolarini (ichaklarni) aniqlash mumkin. Bundan tashqari, qizilo'ngachning oshqozon yarasi, qizilo'ngach divertikullari yoki paraesophageal churra

mavjudligini ham aniqlashingiz mumkin.

Qizilo'ngach va oshqozonning rentgen kontrastli tekshiruvi Italiyaning General kompaniyasining Miratel apparati yordamida amalga oshirildi. Bunda barcha bemorlar vertikal, gorizontol holatda, shuningdek, Trendelenburg holatida tekshiriladi.

Endoskopik tekshiruv RE va uning asoratlari tashxislashning asosiy va eng sezgir usuli hisoblanadi. Bu sizga qizilo'ngachning holatini, DQCH, oshqozon yoki o'n ikki barmoqli ichak yarasi, RE asoratlari, qizilo'ngach yarasi, striktura, Barrett qizilo'ngach va qizilo'ngach qon ketishi kabi mavjudligini aniqlash imkonini beradi. Ayniqsa, qizilo'ngachdagi yallig'lanish va o'sma o'zgarishlarini differentsial tashxislashda endoskopik tekshiruv muhim rol o'ynaydi. Shuningdek, siz paraezofageal limfa tugunlarining holatini baholashingiz mumkin.

1970-yillarda ushbu diagnostika usuli rivojlanishda davom etdi va mutaxassislar yarali chandiqa va tekis ko'tarilgan shaklda saratonni aniqlashlari mumkin bo'ldi. Yillar davomida biopsiyalarning keng qo'llanilishi shilliq qavatni sinchiklab tekshirish va bo'yoqlardan foydalanish bilan endoskopistlarning tajribasi bir necha baravar oshdi. 1980-yillarning boshlarida mahalliy o'zgarishlar bilan erta oshqozon saratoni ham aniqlana boshladi [1, 8, 16, 22].

Hozirgi vaqtda ezofagit darajasini aniqlaydigan ko'plab endoskopik tasniflar mavjud. Ular orasida eng keng tarqalgani **M. Savari va G. Miller** tomonidan taklif qilingan ezofagit tasnifidir:

I bosqich - distal qizilo'ngach shilliq qavatining diffuz yoki o'choqli giperemiyasi, Z - chizig'idan yuqoriga qarab tarqaladigan individual qo'shilmagan eroziyalar ;

II bosqich - eroziyalarning birlashish, lekin butun shilliq qavat yuzasini qoplamaydi ;

III bosqich - eroziyalarning birlashishi va butun shilliq qavat yuzasini qoplash;

IV bosqich - qizilo'ngachning surunkali yaralari, fibroz stenoz, qizilo'ngach epiteliysining ustunli metaplaziyasi (Barret qizilo'ngachi).

Endoskopik tekshiruv vaqtida metaplaziya o'choqlarini samarali farqlash uchun - bo'yoqlardan foydalanish - xromoskopik usul (2% Lugol eritmasi, metilen ko'ki, 1% sirka kislotasi eritmasi, 1% neytral qizil indikator va b.), kattalashtiruvchi va tor spektrli endoskopiya (NBI rejimi), shuningdek, konfokal lazerli endomikroskopiya yordamida shilliq qavatni tekshirish keng qo'llaniladi [4, 15].

Ezofagomanometriya - qizilo'ngachning butun uzunligi bo'ylab intrakavitar bosimini qayd etish usuli. U qizilo'ngachning motor funksiyasini o'rganish nafaqat PQSning qobiliyatsizligini aniqlashga, balki davolanish samaradorligini baholashga ham imkon beradi.

Qizilo'ngach ichi pH-metriyasi. RE tashxisining yana bir ishonchli usuli hisoblanadi. Turli mualliflarning fikriga ko'ra, ushbu usulning sezgirligi 60 dan 98% gacha. pH-metriya qizilo'ngachga kiradigan oshqozon tarkibining kislotalilik darajasini, kasallikning balandligi va chastotasini aniqlashga imkon beradi .

Asoratlari. Bir qator mualliflarning fikriga ko'ra, RE asoratlari 30-40 % hollarda uchraydi. RE asoratlari asosiy sabablari bemorlarning kech ko'rinishi, konservativ antirefluks terapiyasining samarasizligi, shuningdek bemorlarning davolanishga rezistentligi.

REning eng ko'p uchraydigan asoratlari 2-7% hollarda kuzatiladigan peptik eroziv-yarali ezofagitdir. RE ning yana bir asorati qizilo'ngachning strikturasi bo'lib, yarali nuqsonlar chandiqlanganda paydo bo'ladi. Bu asorat 4-20% hollarda uchraydi [5, 8, 12, 21]. REning yana bir jiddiy asoratlardan biri- qon ketish bo'lib , bemorlarning 4,3-17% da uchraydi .

Eng jiddiy asorat Barrett qizilo'ngachi bo'lib, uning mohiyati distal qizilo'ngach shilliq qavatining silindrsimon oshqozon epiteliyasi bilan almashtirilishi (metaplaziya) hisoblanadi. Ushbu asorat RE bilan og'rigan bemorlarning 8-20 foizida uchraydi. Ushbu asoratning xavfi qizilo'ngach adenokarsinomasining yuqori chastotasidir. [2, 7, 19, 24].

REni davolashning zamonaviy usullari. REni davolash uning simptomlarini yengillashtirish va turli xil asoratlarni rivojlanish xavfini kamaytirishga qaratilgan . Shuning uchun davolash bir necha yo'nalishda amalga oshiriladi: konservativ, endoskopik terapiya va jarrohlik davolash.

I. Konservativ terapiya.

Asosiy medikamentoz terapiya quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi :

- Antatsidlar (Maaloks, Almagel va boshqalar),

- H2-gistamin blokatorlari (Ranitidin, Famotidin, Kvamatel va boshqalar),
- Proton pompa ingibitorlari (PPI) (Omeprazol, Pantoprozol va boshq.),
- prokinetiklar (Motilium, Serukal va boshq.);

Konservativ terapiyaning kamchiliklari shundaki, u PQS yetishmovchiligining sabablarini bartaraf etmaydi, safro kislotalari va o'n ikki barmoqli ichak tarkibining qizilo'ngachga patologik ta'sirini kamaytirmaydi va RE asoratlarini rivojlanish xavfini yo'qotmaydi.

II. Endoskopik aralashuvlar.

Oxirgi yillarda bipolyar va ko'p qutbli elektrokoagulyatsiya, fotodinamik terapiya va metaplastik epiteliyning lazer bilan ablatsiyasi kabi yangi minimal invaziv endoskopik aralashuvlar jadal rivojlanmoqda.

Metaplaziya o'choqlarining argon plazmasi koagulyatsiyasi (APK) – bu qizilo'ngachning shilliq qavatining o'zgargan joylarini yo'q qilish uchun yuqori chastotali oqimdan foydalanadi, bu shilliq qavatga kontaktsiz tarzda – ionlangan elektr o'tkazuvchan gaz argon orqali uzatiladi. , aniqrog'i, argon plazmasi REni davolash uchun ham qo'llaniladi[59; 59-67, 129-betlar; 126-138-betlar].

III. Jarrohlik davolash.

RE bilan og'riqan bemorlarning taxminan 5-10 foizida konservativ davo kutilgan natijalarni bermaydi va shuning uchun jarrohlik davolash usullari qo'llaniladi.

REni jarrohlik davolashning asosiy afzalliklari:

- Asosan, konservativ terapiya simptomlarni yengillashtiradi, operatsiyalar yordamida reflyuksiyaning asosiy sabablarini yo'q qilish mumkin;
- bemorlarning 90% dan ko'prog'ida ijobiy natijalar kuzatiladi;
- doimiy dori qabuliga bo'lgan ehtiyojning kamayishi.

Daniyada yiliga 100 ming aholiga 788 ta antirefluks operatsiyasi amalga oshiriladi. Ularning ta'kidlashicha, bu boshqa Skandinaviya mamlakatlariga qaraganda deyarli uch baravar kam. AQSHda RE uchun yiliga taxminan 200 000 laparoskopik Nissen operatsiyalari amalga oshiriladi. Ushbu ma'lumotlar uning yuqori chastotasini yana bir bor tasdiqlaydi [9, 14].

Antirefluks operatsiyalarga asosiy ko'rsatmalar (A.N. Ogorokovga ko'ra):

- qizilo'ngachning strikturasi;
- qizilo'ngachning chuqur gemorragik yaralari,
- Barrett qizilo'ngachi.

Antirefluks operatsiyalariga qarshi ko'rsatmalar quyidagilar:

- onkologik kasalliklar;
- turli kasalliklar qon ivishi;
- ruhiy kasalliklar;
- yuqori jarrohlik va anesteziologik xavf (yurak yetishmovchiligi, III-IV dar., jigar sirrozi, jigar yetishmovchiligi, buyrak yetishmovchiligi va boshqalar).

REni jarrohlik davolashning 40 dan ortiq usullari mavjud. Ushbu operatsiyalarning aksariyati faqat tarixiy ahamiyatga ega. Hozirgi vaqtda RE va uning asoratlarini davolash uchun asosan quyidagi operatsiyalar bajariladi [3, 7, 11, 16, 19, 24]:

1. Total fundoplikatsiya (360 °): Nissen-Rossetti , Kollis–Nissen bo'yicha;
2. Qisman fundoplikatsiya (270°) (Belsi bo'yicha oldingi fundoplikatsiya; Dor bo'yicha oldingi gemifundoplikatsiya ; Tupe bo'yicha orqa gemifundoplikatsiya;
3. Hill operatsiyasi - diafragmaning medial oyoqchasiga me'da kichik egriligini mahkamlash;
4. Har xil protezlarni implantatsiya qilish;
5. KEK maydonini jigarning yumaloq bog'lami bilan mustaxkamlash;
6. Qizilo'ngachning ekstirpatsiyasi.

Operatsion usulini tanlash individual ravishda amalga oshiriladi. AQShda Belsi texnikasiga ustunlik beriladi (“floppy Nissen”) va Yevropada esa Nissen-Rossetti, Dor va Tupe qilinadi. REni jarrohlik davolashning ushbu usullarining barchasi ijobiy va salbiy tomonlarga ega. Eng keng tarqalgan va yaxshi o'rganilgan usul - Nissen fundoplikatsiyasi hisoblanadi.

Turli mualliflarning fikriga ko'ra, 4% dan 42 % gacha bo'lgan holatlarda ushbu operatsiyaning o'ziga xos asoratlari rivojlanadi, masalan, choklarning uzilishi va manjetaning yechilishi natijasida REning qaytalanishi, manjetning giperfunktsiyasi tufayli vaqtinchalik yoki doimiy disfagiya, "teleskop" fenomeni - manjetning qizilo'ngachdan pastga siljishi va oshqozonni qisib qo'yishi, intraoperatsion n.vagusning shikastlanishi yoki siqilishi tufayli pilorospazm, "gaz bloat" sindromi - oshqozonni havo bilan to'lishi natijasida kekirish va qusish qobiliyatining yo'qolishi [77 ; 586-594 , 107- betlar ; 531-539 , 120- betlar ; 64-71 , 141- betlar ; 531-539- betlar].

Chenga L.Q. va boshqalar (2019) tadqiqotlariga ko'ra, Barrett qizilo'ngachi bilan og'rigan bemorlarda Collis-Nissen gastropplikatsiyasi REni oldini oladi, PQS gradientini tiklaydi, lekin reflyksning yo'qligiga qaramay, Barret qizilo'ngachi shilliq qavatidagi o'zgarishlarning regressiyasini keltirib chiqarmaydi.

Awad Z.T. va boshqalar (2019) tadqiqotlariga ko'ra, RE va qizilo'ngachning qisqarishi bilan og'rigan bemorlarni davolashda Kollis-Nissen operatsiyasini eng mos deb hisoblaydi. Ular Kollis-Nissen operatsiyasini torakoskopik yordam bilan laparoskopik usulda ham, ochiq transtorakal yo'l bilan ham amalga oshirdilar.

Antirefluks jarrohlikda minimal invaziv usullar joriy etilganidan beri ko'p yillar o'tdi. Nafaqat Nissen, Tupe , Dor va Hill fundoplikatsiyalari laparoskopik usulda, balki Kollis-Nissen operatsiyasi va laparoskopik transhiatal ezofagoektomiya operatsiyasi ham amalga oshiriladi. Bu operatsiyalar zoq muddatli dori terapiyasiga muqobil sifatida tobora ko'proq foydalanilmoqda. Ammo laparoskopik fundoplikatsiya ham ochiq antirefluks operatsiyalari kabi, ko'pincha o'ziga xos postfundoplikatsion asoratlarga olib keladi.

REni davolashda patogenetik jihatdan oqlangan operatsiya deb fundoplikatsiya va SPVni hisoblashadi, chunki fundoplikatsiya oshqozonning kardial qismini mobilizatsiya va denervatsiyasiga olib keladi. SPVdan keyin gastrin darajasi oshadi, oshqozon sekretsiyasi kamayadi va PQS tonusi oshadi.

Chernousov A.F. modifikatsiyasi klassik Nissen fundoplikatsiyasiga qaraganda yaxshiroq natijalar berdi. Bunday holda, oshqozon kichik egriligi va kardiyasi mobilizatsiyasidan keyin qizilo'ngachining abdominal qismida vagus nervlarining asosiy tarmoqlarini va ikkala Latarge nervlarini saqlaydigan "fundoplikatsion manjet" hosil bo'ladi.

Jarrohlik davolashning asoratlari.

Jarrohlik davolash usullarining asoratlari rivojlanish ehtimoli aralashuv turiga, jarrohlik yordami sifatiga bog'liq bo'lib, 2-10% ni tashkil qiladi.

Maxsus asoratlarga quyidagilar kiradi:

- «gas bloat» sindromi;
- operatsiyadan keyingi disfagiya;
- n. vagusning shikastlanishi;
- "demping sindromi";
- diareya;
- oshqozon yarasi;
- qizilo'ngachning pastki qismini noto'g'ri mahkamlash natijasida oshqozon tubinig siljishi;
- oshqozon oqmalarining shakllanishi;
- manjetning sirpanishi - "teleskop" fenomeni ("slipped Nissen" - "sirpanuvchi Nissen").

Xulosa. Shunday qilib, bugungi kunda zamonaviy endoskopiya va jarrohlikning dolzarb muammolaridan biri RE bilan qizilo'ngach shilliq qavatining patologik holatini tashxislash va davolash usullarini takomillashtirishdir. Turli endoskopik aralashuvlarni qo'llash, REning murakkab shakllarini kompleks davolashda lazer yordamida mahalliy endoskopik davolashning yangi usullarini qo'llash uchun ko'rsatmalarni aniqlash meta- va displastik jarayonni qisqartiradi, RE retsidivi va asoratlari sonini kamaytiradi.

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9 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

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